

Thy Will Be Done: Prayer, Compassion and Tenderness

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These days corona pandemic, which we are experiencing so intensely, are to be in the annals of history. No time in the past had had brought the whole world to a standstill. Catastrophe has struck the world in the form of COVID- 19. Overconfidence, carelessness and sheer individualism has fuelled the death toll to unimaginable figures, in twenty first millennium. Quarantine has brought us to an unimagined situation where we are left with ourselves, isolated from the rush of the world. True to political observations of the political scientist, Benedict Anderson, nations have become mere “imagined communities” and the one last meeting point is humanity. Even the most powerful states have been brought to its knees. In the midst of this crisis, we also see the martyrs of today’s world; doctors, nurses, health workers, police etc. forsaking their lives for a better humanity.

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Sparks of Creativity

Human being as a living being encompassing spiritual, social, economic, cultural and social aspects has been evolving so fast that today in the dawn of twenty first we humans claimed to have reached its zenith. From talking about Super humans, Cyborg, Missions to Mars, a small virus has made a paradigm shift in the course of history. The Quarantine days has once again reminded us of the fragility of human race and of the illusionary causes behind which we were rushing. The Biblical

Quarantine day where Jesus isolated himself to win over the craving for material goods, power and recognition helped foster, illustrate and spread the vibe of the Kingdom of God. Crammed into households cautiously we are but to live this out gracefully. As law abiding citizen of a modern nation state, we are to adjust to these constraints with complete cooperation. We are sure to experience loneliness, but, instead of giving up remember that God has endowed us with the power to turn it into solitude. It is here, where creativity sparks and thus something meaningful takes birth.

Ushering a New Order

The end of the pandemic is sure to usher a new order; with the collapse of the first world countries, priorities would be reorganized, and thus every aspect of life would hopefully be renewed. The signs of times along with the Gospel Values strongly recommends a complete 'Metanoia' with strong roots and convictions that would usher radical steps and to warn against any compromise as death toll for ourselves.

It is a natural that at troubled times like these God comes under fire. Before we do so there is a lot that we have done. reckless exploitation, dumping of waste and harmful materials, all kinds of pollution, depletion of resources and extinction of animals were at an all-time high. Even amidst these crises the humanity was pretending as if nothing had ever happened. God who knows everything is sure to have a better plan of prosperity and hope for humanity. "For I know the plans I have for you," declares the Lord, "plans to prosper you and not to harm you, plans to give you hope and a future." That plan is related to the Kingdom of God that has already dawned among us ("already, not yet").

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Thine Be Done

As committed Christians, our response is same as of the Son of Man when he says "Not my will, but thine be done." It's high time that we stop our reckless exploitation and humble ourselves. Pope Francis in his exhortation recently said "In these days of trial, as humanity trembles at the threat of coronavirus pandemic, I propose that all Christians join their voices together to heaven; to respond to the pandemic of virus with the universality of prayer, compassion and tenderness."

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